

TRUMP'S BOARD OF PEACE FOR GAZA: RECONSTRUCTION OF GAZA OR A NEW WORLD ORDER

Dr. Muhammad Tariq^{*1}, Yasir Mahmood Hameed Ullah², Saad Gul³

^{*1}Lecturer Department of Political Science Hazara University Mansehra

²B S Political Science Department of Political Science Hazara University Mansehra

³Lecturer Government Degree College Havelian, Abbottabad

¹muhammadtariq@hu.edu.pk, ²yasir.khattak106@gmail.com, ³saadgul3358@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Muhammad Tariq

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18455485>

Received	Accepted	Published
06 December 2025	16 January 2026	31 January 2026

ABSTRACT

Trump's Board of Peace for Gaza has gained great momentum on account of the ceasefire in Gaza and efforts for the resolution of the issue of Palestine. The initiative for peace was taken by the US President, Donald Trump in October 2025, followed by the recent initiative of the establishment of the 'Board of Peace'. Many countries of the world have shown their interest to join the board; however the invitation to get a permanent seat on payment of \$1billion during the first year of the board has made it another organization like the United Nations or the establishment of another New World Order by Trump. The study aims at analyzing the Board of Peace for Gaza by Trump, or quest for another New World Order. Main findings of the study conclude that the life-long chairmanship of the board by Trump, coupled with the veto power and his invitation to the states for joining membership of the board is more like the establishment of another world organization or quest for another new world order led by Donald Trump.

Keywords: Board, Peace, Gaza, Reconstruction, World, Organization

INTRODUCTION

The Gaza Peace plan was announced by the President of the United States, Donald Trump on October 13, 2025 on the occasion of his meeting the global leaders (Middleeast, 2025). The plan mainly deals with the core issue of ceasefire and remains silent about the establishment of a free and independent Palestine for which the Hamas has been fighting for a long time (Middleeast, 2025). For all practical purposes a true peace plan should have the four cardinal principles; the end of Israeli genocide in the Palestinian territory, measures for the disarmament of Hamas, inclusion of Palestine to the ambit of the United Nations and the normalizations of relations

between Israel and the Palestine (Middleeast, 2025)(Tariq, Amair, & Bano, 2025). Even after efforts of October 2025 by the world community for bringing peace and stability in the Middle East has failed and the Palestinians are still crying for peace and an independent state.

It is a matter of concern for the global community that 58 years have elapsed since the occupation of Palestine by the Israel. Many efforts were made from time to time to find a viable solution for the resolution of the dispute but of no avail. The Balfour Declaration was issued for the establishment of Jewish homeland in Palestine, the conflict between Israel and Palestine exists.

The Oslo Accords, signed in 1993 provided for the social change, leading towards the establishment of a Palestinian state and resolution of the dispute in true spirit (Nichols, 2025). Mutual recognition by the two groups; Israel's recognition of the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) and Palestinians' recognition of the Israeli state led to the normalization of relations between Palestine and Israel (Nichols, 2025). Normalization of relations was established by the PLO-run Palestine Authority as envisaged by the Oslo Accords. Efforts were made from time to time to find out a viable solution to the issue pondering over options for the recognition of each other as states but all efforts are still not fruitful.

Palestine-Israel Conflict

The Palestine-Israel conflict dates back to more than a 100-years period time, with the crises building from the UN 1947 initial UN partition plan to the 1973 Yom Kippur War, to the recent Israel-Hamas war that sparked in 2023 (Salem, 2025). The recent escalation between Israel and Hamas ignited in October 2023 when the two groups entered into direct confrontation resulting in the death of many people. Hamas is considered to have taken the initiative of the offensive resulting in the death-casualties of hundreds of people. The offensive was retaliated by Israel with more intensity and strength killing thousands of Palestinians, injuries o people and their being made homeless. Efforts were taken twice to reach a viable ceasefire in November 2023 and March 2025 respectively but all in vain (Ferragamo, 2025). Despite many efforts taken towards the bringing of peace and stability in the region including the Camp David Accords, the Oslo Accords of 1992, and the 2020 Abraham Accords, conflict still persists. (Salem, 2025). The Palestine-Israel conflict has been one of the deadliest conflicts in the recent history that has caused great loss to the people of Palestine. The recent war started on October 7, 2023 when 1,200 Israelis and foreigners were killed as a result of the war, followed by more than 67, 000 Palestinians killed since the war broke out (Hedy Amir, 2025). A number of Israelis have also been captured in

the recent war and have been released as a result of the peace deal.

To bring an end to the conflict and reach out a ceasefire, the Gaza Peace Plan was signed between Israel and Palestine in October 2025 in the presence of the US President, Donald Trump, and Prime Minister of Pakistan, Shahbaz Sharif (Ferragamo, 2025). The historic event came on October 8, 2025 when the Israeli government and Hamas agreed on the first part of the peace plan proposed by the US President, Donald Trump resulting in cessation of hostilities on October 10, 2025. The event was attended by more than twenty countries in *Sharm-el-Sheikh*, Egypt paving the way for the ceasefire in Gaza though neither Israel nor Hamas made their representation on the occasion (Ferragamo, 2025). The absence of both Israel and Palestine in event puts a question mark on the applicability of the peace plan because these two are the contending parties whereby the former is suppressing the freedom struggle of the later while the latter is trying its best to retaliate with limited resources of warfare technology (Tariq , Amair, & Bano, 2025).

Gaza Board of Peace

US President has invited countries to pay 1\$ billion in exchange for a permanent seat on a newly proposed initiative known as the 'Board of Peace' (Dawn, 2026). The body was initially envisioned as a mechanism to bring peace in the Palestinian territory as a result of Israel's war while its charter does not restrict its mandate solely to the occupied Palestinian area (Dawn, 2026). Several countries of the world including Pakistan have been approached to join the board. Prime Minister, Shahbaz Sharif accepted the invitation by participating in the initiative with the aim of 'achieving lasting peace in Gaza' (Dawn, 2026). The board will be headed by the US President, Donald Trump and will be described as an 'international organization' seeking to promote stability, restore dependable and lawful governance, and secure enduring peace in the areas affected or threatened by the conflict' (Boxerman & Kershner, 2026)'. The board will be entrusted with the functions of undertaking peace building measures as enshrined in the international law.

The charter provides for the post of a chairman where Donald Trump will serve as the first chairman of the board by also acting as the first representative of the United States. The chairman shall have the exclusive authority to create, modify or dissolve subsidiary entities as necessary or appropriate to fulfill the mission of the Board of Peace (Dawn, 2026). The basic purpose of the board is initially to supervise the reconstruction of Gaza. The chairman of the board, Trump, will appoint members of the executive board to be described as the 'leaders of global stature' to be appointed for a period of two years and can be removed by the chairman. The chairman can also be replaced either through his voluntary resignation or as a result of incapacity.

Eligibility for Membership of Executive Board

Membership of the board is limited to a maximum period of three years however; contributors to pay more than US \$1,000,000,000 in cash during the first year, is exempted from this restriction (Dawn, 2026). Secretary of State, Marco Rubio and Trump's son in law, Jared Kushner is among those exempted from this restriction. The US President may have exclusive powers to invite states for membership who will be represented by their heads of state or government. The board will be convened at least once a year for voting session where each country will have a single vote. Decisions of the board will require a majority of members present during voting session and will be subject to the approval of the chairman who will only cast his vote in case of a tie (Dawn, 2026).

The main purpose of the board will be to see implementation of the objectives of the board to be chaired by the US President, Donald Trump. The board will comprise seven members;

- US Secretary of State Marco Rubio
- Steve Witkoff, Trump's special negotiator
- Jared Kushner, Trump's son-in law
- Tony Blair, former British Prime Minister
- Marc Rowan, US billionaire financier
- Ajay Banga, President of the World Bank
- Robert Gabriel, a close Trump associate serving on the US National Security Council

Dozens of countries including Pakistan have confirmed the invitations being received. China,

India, Russia, Ukraine and Canada have confirmed invitations while France has refused the invitation. Confirmation of invitations have also been expressed by Egypt and Argentine while other countries to have acknowledged invitations include Jordan, Brazil, Paraguay, Pakistan as well as several states of Europe, Central Asia and the middle East (Dawn, 2026). Countries who have agreed to become members include Vietnam, Hungary while Canada has shown willingness but have refused to pay \$1 billion for permanent membership. It is also important to mention whether Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Morocco, and Vietnam will be willing to pay \$1 billion contribution.

Joint Statement on the Board of Peace

The Ministers of Foreign Affairs of Islamic Republic of Pakistan, the Arab Republic of the Egypt, the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, the United Arab Emirates, the Republic of Indonesia, the Republic of Turkiye, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and the State of Qatar welcomed the invitation extended by President Trump for joining the Board of Peace (Affairs, 2026). The Ministers jointly announced their countries' shared decision to join the Board of Peace. Each country will sign the joining documents as per its respective relevant legal and other necessary procedures, including Egypt, Pakistan and the UAE, that have already expressed their willingness to join (Affairs, 2026). The ministers reiterate their countries' support for the peace initiatives taken by Donald Trump for the accomplishment of the peace mission through the Board of Peace as a transitional administration, as set out in the Comprehensive Plan to end the Gaza Conflict. The board has been endorsed by the United Nations Security Council Resolution 2803, aiming at the permanent ceasefire coupled with the reconstruction of Gaza and advancing a just and lasting peace while furthering the cause of Palestinian right to self-determination as enshrined by the international law (Affairs, 2026). Nine countries in the Middle East and Asia have expressed their intention to join the US President's 'Board of Peace' in the Gaza Strip with the aim to secure a permanent ceasefire in the Palestinian territory (Staff, 2026). The aim of the

board is to achieve a consolidating and permanent ceasefire in the Palestinian region, supporting the measures for the reconstruction of Gaza and efforts for advancing a just and long lasting peace while furthering the cause of the right of self-determination and statehood (Staff, 2026). The creation of Palestinian State in accordance with the dictum of international law would pave the way for security and stability of all the countries of the region. Kuwait has also expressed its concern regarding Trump's invitation for joining the board. Trump's initiative for establishing a 'Board of Peace' for the resolution of the Palestine dispute is part of his 20-point peace plan aimed at the ceasefire and creation of an independent Palestinian State (Staff, 2026). The board has been tasked with the overseeing of a Palestinian technocratic committee tasked with managing the day-to-day affairs of the Gaza Strip.

The constitution of board has also faced criticism from different quarters regarding the functioning of a US-led mechanism in Gaza. It has also been criticized on the inclusion of several Israeli supporters in the board of peace, as well as, participation of Israeli Prime Minister, Benjamin Netanyahu, who faces arrest warrant from the International Criminal Court (Staff, 2026). Gaza resident, al-Sandawi, told Al Jazeera in the Gaza City that Netanyahu is the cause of the war. The Palestinian Health Ministry has reported that about 466 Palestinians have been killed during the Israeli attacks on Gaza since the US-brokered ceasefire came into force in October 2025.

Trump's new Board of Peace for resolving global conflicts has drawn sharp cynicism from some of the US allies, criticizing that it would dismantle the post-World War II international system (Kershner, 2026). The body largely comprising the heads of state or government was originally expected to supervise the ceasefire between Israel and Palestine. The charter of the board gives extensive, global mandate in resolving the conflicts faced by the world. Some analysts are of the view that the US President, Donald Trump is trying to create a rival forum to the United Nations putting him in charge of the forum (Kershner, 2026). As chairman of the board, Trump will have veto power over some of the decisions and has also urged the heads of

the states and governments to contribute \$1 billion for getting permanent seat in the board of peace. But it is also worth mentioning that over 20 countries have accepted the invitation for membership which they can retain for the first three years while several allies of the US including a number of European Countries have also declined the offer (Kershner, 2026).

Trump envisions a broader role for the board as per a copy of the charter shared with The New York Times stating that the board aims at securing peace in the areas affected or threatened by conflict not just Gaza but in other parts of the world too (Boxerman & Kershner, 2026). The board foresees a more effective and stronger international peace-building body than the United Nations (Boxerman & Kershner, 2026). Donald Trump has also questioned the validity of the UN accusing it of a waste and liberal bias (Boxerman & Kershner, 2026). The charter invests considerable power in Trump even after he leaves the office of presidency. Besides his veto power, he would also be able to nominate his own successor and would be empowered to enact resolutions or other directives for carrying out the mission of the board.

The 'Board of Peace' though at its first glance seems to maintain peace and order in the Gaza Strip and debars Israel from the use of force against the Palestinian people yet it appears to be a stronger body than even the UN. The chairman of the board has been vested with supreme powers using the power of veto and even empowers him to remain in power after quitting the office of presidency. The invitation to contribute \$1 billion for procuring a permanent seat in the Board of Peace is another of concern as this would make the board more personal besides the permanent position of Donald Trump as its chairman. The UN has membership of the entire countries of the world and has strong forums like the General Assembly and Security Council but the irony of the fact is most of the allies of the US including the European Countries have declined the offer of joining the board.

Twenty founding countries of the world including the United States, attended a signing

ceremony in Davos, Switzerland on January 22, 2026 (Boxerman & Kershner, 2026). Those who attended the ceremony include Argentina, Hungary, Indonesia, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, and Qatar. Pakistani Prime Minister, Shahbaz Sharif signed the Board of Peace during the ceremony in Davos on January 22, 2026 (Khwaja, 2026). The initiative was taken by Pakistan to participate in the peace-focused platform amid continued international efforts for addressing the humanitarian and political fallout of the Gaza conflict (Khwaja, 2026). The proposed charter has divided some of the United States' longtime allies about joining the board. France, Britain, Norway, and Sweden have refused to join the board at this time arguing that it has raised questions regarding international law and the respect for the United Nations' role in the world. British Foreign Minister, Yvette Cooper, has expressed concerns about the prospect of Russia being part of the Board of Peace despite the fact that it has invaded Ukraine.

Powers and Functions of the Board of Peace

The Board of Peace is an international organization comprising thirteen chapters; each chapter has been assigned a specific power and function. Chapter 1st seeks to promote stability, restore dependable and lawful governance, and secure enduring peace in the areas affected or threatened by conflict (Jacob, 2026). It aims at undertaking peace-building in accordance with the international law and as may be approved in accordance with this charter, including the development and dissemination of best practices capable of being applied by all the nations and communities seeing peace (Jacob, 2026) & (Affairs, 2026). No member state shall serve the board for more than three years or unless removed by the chairman of the board. This condition shall not apply to member states who contribute more than USD \$1, 000,000,000 in cash to the Board of Peace during the first year of the Charter's entry into force (Jacob, 2026). However, any member may also withdraw from the board upon written notice to the chairman of the board.

The board has been entrusted with powers and functions as enshrined in the charter. The board shall vote on all proposals on its agenda, with respect to the annual budgets, the establishment of subsidiary entities, the appointment of senior executive officers and major policy disseminations (Jacob, 2026). Voting meetings shall be convened at least once a year or at such locations and additional times as deemed fit by the chairman. Each member state will have one vote and decisions will be made on basis of majority of cast votes with chairman to exercise the right to vote in case of a tie. The chairman will be empowered to create, modify, or dissolve subsidiary entities as necessary or appropriate to fulfill the mission of the Board of Peace (Jacob, 2026). The chairman may establish sub-committees as appropriate and shall set the mandate, structure and governance rules for such committees (Jacob, 2026).

The charter talks about the composition of the Executive Board to be selected by the chairman and will have duration of two years. The Executive Board will be led by the Chief Executive to be nominated by the chairman through a majority of votes. The Chief Executive shall convene the Executive Board every two weeks for the first three months following its establishment and on a monthly basis thereafter, with additional meetings convened as the Chief Executive deems appropriate (Jacob, 2026). The Executive Board shall make decisions by a majority of its members present and voting, including the Chief Executive with the decisions to come into force immediately, subject to approval by the chairman. Chapter 5 deals with the financing of the Board of Peace, which will be open to voluntary funding from member states, other states, organizations and other sources willing to contribute (Jacob, 2026). Chapter 6 gives legal coverage and protection to the Board of Peace to have legal capacity as may be necessary to the pursuit of their mission including the capacity to enter into contract.

Resolution of Disputes

Internal disputes amongst the member states of the Board of Peace and personnel with respect to matters pertaining to the Board of Peace can be resolved through amicable collaboration,

consistent with the authorities of the organization established by the charter with the chairman as the final authority for such matters. Any amendment to the charter can be proposed provided it is supported by at least 1/3rd of the member states of the Board of Peace. Proposal for such amendment can be circulated amongst the member states at least thirty days before voting and can be amended by a 2/3rd majority (Jacob, 2026). But the main function of the Board is to oversee a National Committee for the administration of Gaza comprising Palestinian technocrats as administrators (Chenoy, 2026). An important element that should have been given priority is the absence of any reference to Palestinian rights, interests, rehabilitation, land, livelihood or statehood (Chenoy, 2026). The focus of the Board appears more on the process of reconstruction rather than justice and focus on the right to self-determination of the Palestinian people.

The agonizing fact is that the Israeli genocide continues in Gaza in different names, sometimes under the guise of other international events like Greenland's fate or Ukraine's dark bitter winter (Chenoy, 2026). According to a report of January 21, 2026 Israel seized and destroyed the UN Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA) for Palestine, in sheer violation of international law leaving Gaza with minimum support for its besieged population (Chenoy, 2026). Health Authorities of Gaza testify that 70,000 people have been killed in the Gaza Strip, with survivors traumatized and besieged (Chenoy, 2026). Peace and stability is much necessary in the Gaza Strip and can be possible only with complete ceasefire and giving the right of self-determination to the Palestinian people. Complete ceasefire coupled with no use of force against the people of Palestine and peaceful acts of protests by the Palestinian can make the Board of Peace more effective and would lead towards the process of reconstruction and resolution of disputes. Resolving the issue of Palestine on priority basis can build the trust of the regional and the international community as other conflicts or threats faced any community can better be resolved.

Discussion and Conclusion

The board of Peace for Gaza as formed by the President of the United States has raised some questions as a substitute for the United Nations or Trump's quest for a 'New World Order' making him more powerful. The strength of the Board can be guessed from the fact that it gives numerous powers to the chairman of the board besides giving him the power to retain the office of the chairmanship even after he leaves White House. The invitation by Trump to countries to have permanent seat on contribution of \$ 1 billion USD during the first year is another area of concern for the world. The rest of the states will have duration of three years membership, unless removed by the chairman of the board. Experts are of the view that though the Board of Peace initially aims at resolving the issue of Gaza and stopping the genocide of the Palestinians by the Israel yet it may be more than the restoration of peace in the Gaza Strip. From its appearance it seems to be a substitute of the United Nations or quest for another New World Order.

The Board of Peace initially aims at bringing peace in the areas affected or threatened by conflict but the US may use it for ulterior motives. The invitation by the US President, Trump to join the Board of Peace in itself is a tantamount of making the US President a stronger actor in the world politics. Even the offer by contributing \$1 billion to the board during the first year is another area of concern for the world powers since it may be another international organization with the US president having the veto power over the decisions made by the member states. Moreover, the contribution of \$ 1 billion will procure a permanent seat for the member state in the Board of Peace. The power of veto to be exercised by Donald Trump even after he relinquishes the office of US Presidency, also questions the validity of the board as making it more like something personal proprietary rights. For an organization it is necessary that the constituent bodies should be made through consultation by the contracting states and rules of business be devised by the states through mutual consensus. The nature of permanent or temporary membership can be determined by the member states on the basis of rotation and their

involvement in world politics. The body should have President, a Secretary General and supporting staff with a Headquarter where the entire staff should have their role to play for the smooth and harmonious functioning of the organization. Even the use of veto power by any member state may put the validity of other states as being not parallel to the other states; it would be in the best interest of the member states to have parity and equality in all matters of importance. Enjoying equal powers by all the member states would not make other member states as inferior to other states. In the same way, the President of the Board of Peace should have a fixed tenure with just tenure provided he or she gets majority of votes through voting by all the member states.

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